

Note on the Permeability of Membranes.

BY

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Some years ago Barlow (*Phil. Mag.*, (6), 10, 1; 1906, 11, 595) showed that the presence of alcohol made a copper ferrocyanide membrane permeable to sugar, though no explanation was given. In a recent paper, Bancroft and Gurchot (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, 28, 1279) have explained this fact on the assumption that alcohol coagulates the membrane, thus making it permeable to sugar. "Since sugar is insoluble in alcohol, it is clear that the alcohol cannot make the copper ferrocyanide membrane permeable to sugar by increasing the solubility of the sugar in the membrane. There must therefore have been a fundamental change."

Less than two per cent. of methyl alcohol was sufficient to make the copper ferrocyanide membrane permeable to sugar. With the higher alcohols the necessary concentrations were much lower. A forty per cent. methyl alcohol coagulated a solution of copper ferrocyanide, and the authors consider that the precipitation of the solution is a much less sensitive test than the one for the permeability of the membrane, though it supports their explanation.

In a recent paper (Sen, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 28, 517) a study has been made on the stability of copper ferrocyanide sol, and it was found that alcohol could not coagulate the sol in the absence of electrolytes under the experimental conditions. I have therefore made some more experiments with a freshly prepared and concentrated sol of copper ferrocyanide with a view to study under

what conditions colloidal copper ferrocyanide is precipitated by alcohols. I shall only summarise the results obtained by me.

(1) Colloidal copper ferrocyanide can be precipitated by means of alcohols in presence of small quantities of electrolytes. The purer the sol the greater is its stability towards alcohols.

(2) A concentrated sol can be coagulated more easily than a dilute sol. Ethyl alcohol in a concentration of sixty per cent. coagulated the sol in one hour whereas with a half-diluted sample of the same sol no sign of coagulation was visible even after seventy hours.

(3) With methyl, ethyl, propyl and butyl alcohols, the higher the alcohol, the greater is the precipitating power.

These results therefore support the views of Bancroft and Gurchot. In my previous paper a dilute sol was used and the coagulation time was only two hours with the alcohols. Further the concentrations of the alcohols added were never high. Hence no coagulation of the sol was observed. The results of this paper further show that the highly concentrated membranes of copper ferrocyanide should be more sensitive to alcohols than the dilute ones. It is also probable, as Tinker (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1916, 92, 364) has shown, that stable membranes always contain traces of either copper sulphate or potassium sulphate, which means a sensitisation in presence of alcohols. Greater sensitiveness to higher alcohols is also explained by my results, as they have greater coagulating action.

Though this simple and interesting explanation of Bancroft and Gurchot has been supported by my qualitative experiments, there is an apparent difficulty in extending this to some other cases. Thus Traube (*Archiv. Anat. Physiol. und Wissenschaft. Medizin*, pp. 87-165, 1887) showed that copper ferrocyanide is not permeable to either

of the solutions from which it is formed, nor to barium chloride, calcium chloride, ammonium sulphate, barium nitrate, sugar, etc. ; it is, however, permeable to potassium chloride. There is no reason why salts of barium or calcium should not be permeable, for these salts are powerful precipitants of the copper ferrocyanide membranes, unless it is assumed that they were used in very dilute solutions in which case complete adsorption of the cations took place by the negative membrane (Frankert and Wilkinson, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, 28, 651). The membrane ought to be permeable to moderate concentrations of barium chloride, unless, however, the charge on the membrane be reversed in which case negative osmosis shall occur, because negative osmosis is dependent on the electrical polarisation of the capillaries of the membranes, and this polarisation is brought about by ionic adsorption (*cf.* Bartell *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 36, 646 ; Bartell and Hocker, *ibid.*, 1916, 38, 1029, 1036 ; Bartell and Madison, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1920, 24, 593). Potassium chloride may not be permeable depending on the amount of its adsorption, for selective adsorption has an important part to play in the permeability of substances, but this side of the problem is in a very unsatisfactory state.*

Lastly, it may be said that the proofs given in the paper of Bancroft and Gurchot and in this one as regards the coagulation points of view are of indirect nature. A direct method would be to utilise Tinker's methods (*loc. cit.*) and get some microphotographs of copper ferro-

* In this connection it may be stated that H. N. Morse has reported that changes of structure take place when a copper ferrocyanide membrane is bathed by various aqueous salt solutions. They also take place with zinc ferrocyanide and manganese ferrocyanide even in water (*Report on Osmotic Pressure of Aqueous Solutions*, Chaps. IV and XI, Carnegie Institute of Washington, 1914).

cyanide and other membranes with drops of dilute alcohol and other acids added to them. The results would show definitely whether we are getting coagulation or not in these cases.

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A Note on an Improved Device for Working a Thermostat at Low Temperatures.

BY

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The general practice in physical chemistry is to take standard measurements at 18°C or 25°C. At Bombay the temperature of the atmosphere rarely falls below 25°C and the necessity is felt of fitting up a thermostat which would work conveniently and smoothly at 25°C.

Foote (*Z. physical. Chem.*, 1906, 33, 740) has described a thermo-regulator suitable for running a thermostat at low temperatures. The thermo-regulator is filled with toluene and mercury as the ordinary gas thermo-regulator. The head of the regulator *D* contains an inlet tube *F* and two exit tubes *E* and *G*. The method of its working, as suggested by Foote, is to admit ice-cold water continuously into the regulator by the tube *F*. When the temperature of the thermostat rises above the one required, ice-cold water entering the regulator by the tube *F* falls out from the tube *G* into the thermostat and thus lowers the temperature of the thermostat. But